

BIM

prove

D2.5 – Safety- critical situation detection – V2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 958450. This document reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

D2.5 Safety-critical situation detection – V2

Project Title	Improving Building Information Modelling by Realtime Tracing of Construction Processes
Project Acronym	BIMprove
Grant Agreement No	958450
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	Industrial Sustainability
Start Date of Project	1st September 2020
Duration of Project	36 Months

Name and Number of the deliverable	2.5 – Safety-critical situation detection – V2
Related WP number and name	WP2 Components, technologies & functionalities
Deliverable dissemination level	Public
Deliverable due date	30 November 2022
Deliverable submission date	30 November 2022
Task leader/Main author	Anu Purhonen (VTT)
Contributing partners	Tommi Aihkisalo (VTT), Ilkka Niskanen (VTT), Morten Lind (SINTEF), Mats Larsen (SINTEF)
Reviewer(s)	Christian Dalheim Øien (SINTEF)

Abstract

This deliverable describes how to use the Risk Object Visual Analysis System (ROVAS) for automatic detection of safety measures, especially safety nets, from photographs and 3D point clouds captured at construction sites. It also describes the Risk and Image Data Management Service that has been used to store and provide access to the data created by the ROVAS model. Integration with the Bimsync platform is also elaborated. Finally, links to the experimenting with asset localization and tracking are presented.

Keywords

Safety measures, computer vision, convolutional neural network, YOLO, point clouds, PointPillars, 3D, Asset localization and tracking

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	15 th February 2022	Submitted for internal review	Tommi Aihkisalo (VTT), Ilkka Niskanen (VTT), Anu Purhonen (VTT)
v0.2	24 th February 2022	Ready for SINTEF quality check	Tommi Aihkisalo (VTT), Ilkka Niskanen (VTT), Anu Purhonen (VTT)
v1.0	28 th February 2022	Approved, final version	Christian Dalheim Øien (SINTEF)
v1.1	28th November 2022	Updated version submitted for internal review	Tommi Aihkisalo (VTT), Ilkka Niskanen (VTT), Morten Lind (SINTEF), Mats Larsen (SINTEF)
v1.2	30th November 2022	Ready for quality check	Anu Purhonen (VTT)
V1.3	30th November 2022	Approved, final version	Christian Dalheim Øien (SINTEF)

Disclaimer

This document is provided with no warranties whatsoever, including any warranty of merchantability, non-infringement, fitness for any particular purpose, or any other warranty with respect to any information, result, proposal, specification or sample contained or referred to herein. Any liability, including liability for infringement of any proprietary rights, regarding the use of this document or any information contained herein is disclaimed. No license, express or implied, by estoppel or otherwise, to any intellectual property rights is granted by or in connection with this document. This document is subject to change without notice. BIMprove has been financed with support from the European Commission. This document reflects only the view of the author(s) and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence based on Machine Learning
ALT	Asset Localization and Tracking
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CURL	Client URL
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational state transfer
YOLO	You-Only-Look-Once

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

Contents

1. Introduction.....	8
2. Risk Object Visual Analysis System.....	8
2.1. Utilized Tools, Methods and Materials.....	9
3. 3D Point Cloud Extension.....	14
3.1. Dataset.....	14
3.2. Object Detection Model.....	17
4. Risk and Image Data Management Service.....	20
4.1. Installation of the Risk and Image Data Management Service.....	21
4.2. Testing the installation and provided functionalities.....	21
5. Integration with the Bimsync platform.....	23
5.1. Installation of the Bimsync proxy.....	23
5.2. Testing the installation and provided functionalities.....	23
6. Asset Localization and Tracking.....	24
7. References.....	24

Index of Figures

Figure 1. Labelling tool and VTT sourced image with safety net and barrier labelling.	9
Figure 2 Tiled image samples (3 x 2 tiling) of the augmented data with artificial scaling, shearing, flipping and mosaic of the original dataset images.	11
Figure 3 Partial internal view of the cropped individual floor of the building.	14
Figure 4 Point cloud of the individual floor with a single cube shaped block featuring part of the safety net and barrier cropped to be included in the data set.....	15
Figure 5 The 90 degree flip about the horizontal X-axis in order to improve visibility and resulting detectability of certain shaped objects in this case for the observer.....	16
Figure 6 LabelCloud point cloud labelling tool with a data set sample and added bounding boxes for a safety net (blue) and barrier (green).	17
Figure 7 Risk ontology	20

1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to describe how the functionalities defined in Deliverable 2.4 has been implemented and tested and how they can be taken into use. The images captured from the risk zones can be analysed by the Risk Object Visual Analysis System, ROVAS, for detecting the existence and placement of the required safety structures. The safety structures are expected to mitigate various risks on the construction site locations, e.g. fall risks. The ROVAS can make only positive detections, i.e. confirming the existence of such structures and thus aid inspecting safety structures' readiness state in the locations for safe construction work. The purpose of Risk and Image Data Management Service is to store and provide access to the results created by ROVAS. ROVAS has also been integrated with Bimsync.

Part of safety functionalities is also asset localization and tracking which is only shortly addressed here as it has already been described in other deliverables.

2. Risk Object Visual Analysis System

Risk Object Visual Analysis System, ROVAS, bases on the convolutional neural networks, CNN, for its visual object detection task. CNN based AI/ML models are commonly used in modern computer vision systems and object detection. The deployment of such model as functional part of the ROVAS requires gathering the potentially suitable data, manually labelling the risk objects in the data set, installation of suitable tools and frameworks and training and evaluating maturity of it. The maturity of the model will be evaluated by relational development of the achieved accuracy and loss indicators. This is since systems to compare to are mostly non-existent and there are no common publicly shared datasets for rating CNN models in this specific application domain. The capabilities of the ROVAS with the visual object detection mature model will be exposed through the Internet accessible service interface.

The applied CNN model type here is You Only Look Once, YOLO, as described in [1]. Specifically, we applied the further improved open-source implementation of version 5 available from <https://github.com/ultralytics/yolov5>. This implementation includes also useful scripting and service provisioning examples all licensed with GPL-3.0. For the general principles, intended operational details and limitations see the Deliverable 2.4 Detailed Description of the Safety Functionalities and Worker Notifications.

However, to improve the spatial detection and position determination of the required safety structures, object detection or segmentation could be executed directly on the laser scanned point clouds. While processing point clouds requires a vast amount of computing power, storage space and some point cloud processing limitations, it has been only briefly trialled here to see its viability

in overall. The trials consist of pre-processing and labelling of the point cloud data to create a 3D training data set and training one 3D point cloud object detection model type for the inference testing purposes. Potentially, it could provide a foundation for the 3D extension in ROVAS itself.

2.1. Utilized Tools, Methods and Materials

To implement a ROVAS service, training the AI/ML based computer vision model for object detection is necessary. Preceding that, however, a data collection and annotation of it is required in supervised type of machine learning. The original data was provided by the project partners HRS, VIAS and ZHAW including video recorded by VTT from a construction site in Madrid. The group effort by VTT produced a sufficient labelling of the safety nets, barriers and trash appearing in the digital imagery data for the training purposes. The video material was split into individual frames for the labelling purposes. The publicly available labelled image datasets lacked the required safety related items required for this application and thus provided no solution.

The collected and labelled BIMprove dataset has over 3500 individual images split to training and validation sets of 2700 and 800 images, respectively. Each of the images contain one or more occurrences of the labelled items in bounding boxes including safety net, barrier or trash, totalling over 5500 individual labels. The labelling tool used for the YOLO formatted annotation and labelling purposes to classify and draw bounding boxes was the freely available labellmg tool from <https://github.com/tzutalin/labellmg>. Figure 1 below illustrates the tool and sample image from the dataset with associated labels.

Figure 1. Labellmg tool and VTT sourced image with safety net and barrier labelling.

With the labelled and ready dataset we were able to start training the object detection model. To save time and effort transfer learning was used. This is done by freezing other layers in the model except the backbone responsible for the final object detection and classification and only to train and update those. This transfer learning method saves significant amounts of time and computing resources while producing reasonably accurate models.

The YOLO implementation (<https://github.com/ultralytics/yolov5>) used is built on the pyTorch (<https://pytorch.org/>) machine learning framework capable of accelerating the floating point and matrix operations with GPU. Installation and other requirements see the relevant documentation of pyTorch and yolov5. The YOLO implementation provided ready to use models out of which the base model chosen for this application was large type. This large model has over 4 million trainable parameters already trained with the COCO dataset. i.e. the model is already capable of detecting and locating generic objects in the images present in the COCO dataset, which unfortunately lacks the safety related objects needed here. The transfer learning process will shift the COCO detection capabilities to detect objects in our own BIMprove dataset. The training of the YOLO v5 based detection model was started with the following kind of command and parameters:

```
#python train.py --weights yolov5l.pt --data <path_to_data> --hyp  
data\hyps\hyp.finetune.yaml --epochs 400 --imgsz 960 --workers 3 --freeze 10 --name  
<name_of_session> --batch-size -1 --optimize AdamW --hyp data\hyps\hyp.finetune.yaml
```

This command starts the training session with following parameters:

- Model size – large type with 46642120 parameters in total
- Training epochs – 400
- Input image size – 960 x 960 pixels (optionally 640 for 640x640 pixels)
- Freezing of all layers below layer 10 trained on COCO dataset
- Automated batch size search – settles to 10 on the utilized computer
- Optimizer is AdamW
- Hyper parameters – as provided based on optimization with VOC dataset, initial learning rate is 0.0032

The utilized hyperparameter set activated automated and randomized artificial augmentation of the training dataset. The general intention is to increase the dataset by creating synthetically manipulated copies the original data and thus also improve generalization capabilities of the final model. The hyperparameters activated augmentations with probabilities of 0.898 for scaling, 0.602 for shearing, 0.5 and 0.00856 horizontal and vertical flipping, respectively. Included also was the mosaic effect, which composes the each of the training images from a set of random augmented image samples or even empty spaces. See Figure 2 below for some augmentation examples from

our dataset (sample images from VTT and ZHAW) produced by the YOLO implementation and hyperparameters provided.

Figure 2 Tiled image samples (3 x 2 tiling) of the augmented data with artificial scaling, shearing, flipping and mosaic of the original dataset images.

The final model's detection capabilities are provided as a service through a suitable REST interface. One implementation available at https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_rdc/tree/main/bimprove_rest, in `bimprove_restapi.py` file, loads the model and uses it to analyze the images send to it by HTTP POST. The detection results are returned as JSON text and described in the deliverable D2.4 Detailed Description of the Safety Functionalities and Worker Notifications. Furthermore, additional guidance is provided for unintentional access to the `/v1/risk_objects/` URL with a browser. Some YOLOv5 trained model files are provided in the git repository for testing purposes. Select the needed model by setting the `model_file_name` variable name as required in the `bimprove_rest/bimprove_restapi.py` file. Provided GPU acceleration is available change the model loading target to 'gpu'. See Torch documentation for the required GPU setup procedures.

```
#model = torch.hub.load("ultralytics/yolov5", 'custom', path=model_file_name).to('gpu')
```

```
model = torch.hub.load("ultralytics/yolov5", 'custom', path=model_file_name).to('cpu')
```

A simple request to the service can be made with a sample Python 3 client based on the *requests* library as

```
"""Perform test request"""

import pprint

import requests

DETECTION_URL = http://<SERVICE_URL>/v1/risk_objects/

TEST_IMAGE = "20.jpg"

image_data = open(TEST_IMAGE, "rb").read()

response = requests.post(DETECTION_URL, files={"image": image_data}).json()

pprint.pprint(response)
```

Where <SERVICE_URL> is the address URL of the provided service and TEST_IMAGE a file name of the sample request image. This sample is also available in https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_rdc/blob/8e3f1065440e1a8b6790af2cf2ac6afb727f1396/bimprove_rest/bimprove_example_request.py. With the sample image the response was:

```
[{'class': 1,
  'confidence': 0.414974153,
  'name': 'safety_net',
  'xmax': 1620.0979003906,
  'xmin': 0.0,
  'ymax': 1082.6301269531,
  'ymin': 37.0090942383},
 {'class': 1,
  'confidence': 0.3516817391,
  'name': 'safety_net',
  'xmax': 1724.8165283203,
```

```
'xmin': 810.5069580078,  
'ymax': 610.0239257812,  
'ymin': 4.0267028809},  
{'class': 1,  
'confidence': 0.263441056,  
'name': 'safety_net',  
'xmax': 1870.6253662109,  
'xmin': 507.2440185547,  
'ymax': 1088.0,  
'ymin': 525.5383300781}}
```

The returned ROVAS response contains the detection results encoded as JSON, where

Class – object class: barrier=0 | safety_net=1 | garbage=2

Confidence – detection confidence from 0-1.0

Name – human readable name for the detect object class

x1 – upper left corner x-coordinate of the bounding box

y1 – upper left corner y-coordinate of the bounding box

x2 – lower right corner x-coordinate of the bounding box

y2 – lower right corner y-coordinate of the bounding box

The coordinates are counted as pixels that of the original image dimensions.

All confidence results over 0.5 can be considered quite reliable detections but may vary significantly in practise as most of the available training data was quite homogeneous in image quality and scenery composition. The lower end confidence levels in this example ranging from 0.26 to 0.41 are due to the purposely challenging sample image used. The sample image is an individual captured frame from a video with added challenges coming from the equipment used to record, lightning conditions and distance to the detected nets. See the image in https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_rdc/blob/8e3f1065440e1a8b6790af2cf2ac6afb727f1396/bimprove_rest/madrid_test_image.jpg.

3. 3D Point Cloud Extension

This section briefly illustrates the potential 3D point cloud object detection extension for the ROVAS. It is supposed to detect the same safety nets and barriers from the laser scanned point clouds as the image based ROVAS solution described in the previous section. This section describes the pre-processing and creation of the required data set and the major parts of the applied 3D object detection solution with the results achieved with it.

3.1. Dataset

Along the images utilized in the previous section a set of point clouds were captured too. To see more details about the nature of them see the updated deliverable D2.4 Detailed Description of the Safety Functionalities and Worker Notifications.

The sample starting point is the 23 million point cloud of the building used for the project's case study. The preprocessing of this included cropping to individual floors and then cropping of those to fixed size blocks. Thus, the point cloud was cropped vertically to five individual floors of the building. These cropped floors have visible internal safety nets and arbitrary safety barriers among the structures removing the floors and ceilings from the views. Figure 3 presents an individual corner of the floor on CloudCompare point cloud edit tool.

Figure 3 Partial internal view of the cropped individual floor of the building.

D2.5 Safety-critical situation detection – V2

Furthermore, each of the floors were then cropped to a fixed size block of 5 x 5 units as measured in the CloudCompare tool. This was estimated to produce blocks of around 250 000 points maximum. The starting point of the individual floor and the resulting data set block presented in the Figure 4.

Figure 4 Point cloud of the individual floor with a single cube shaped block featuring part of the safety net and barrier cropped to be included in the data set.

These data set blocks will form the basis of the data set that can be labelled. Here the average number of points in each block is around 250 000 points. The point number limitation was estimated with regards to the computer resources and respective time limitations available for this trial. The point cloud object detection models, like the image-based object detection models, impose a configurable but runtime fixed input data size limit. This is due to the nature of the neural networks ability to only consume fixed size data. Many point cloud object detection models will just drop out the excess or just sample a fixed amount of the points presented. Out of the single large point cloud we were able to source 125 suitable blocks. All empty and those with meaningless number points were left out.

Further processing was still required. The cropped blocks are still scattered in their original locations in the original point clouds coordinate space. This required centering them with the application available at

https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_3D_safety_detection/blob/main/data_utils/center_pcds.py

This can be executed as

```
#python center_pcds.py
```

Note that this and other applications require Open3D and/or Open3D-ML libraries. Follow their respective documentation to install if required. Also see

https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_3D_safety_detection for further information about the expected folder structure etc.

During the model training trials it was realized that the applied model architecture was detecting the objects from the birds-eye-view, BEV, vantage point. This is due to the typical intended use for the point cloud object detection models in autonomous driving or drone flying, where the detection scanner is typically located higher above the ground. This mostly works as the common detectable objects in such cases are vehicles and humans with substantial upper projection surface area. In our case, that of the nets and barriers is much smaller if not even non-existent considering the resolution of the point clouds. To accelerate training and improve the detection results in this case it was advisable to flip point cloud chunks 90 degrees about the horizontal X-axis. This was implemented as post-processing modification step for the dataset. This results the detectable items facing upwards and enhancing the artificial visibility for the observer. In the detection use this is believed to allow detecting the safety nets and barriers on in height restricted spaces. The flip and its effect on enhancing the visibility and detectability for the observer is demonstrated on the Figure 5.

Figure 5 The 90 degree flip about the horizontal X-axis in order to improve visibility and resulting detectability of certain shaped objects in this case for the observer.

The 90 degree flip for the point clouds and the already created labels were done with the application available at https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_3D_safety_detection/blob/main/data_utils/tilt_generate.py

This can be executed as

```
#python tilt_generate.py
```

The same notes and restrictions apply as for the previous centering application.

The gathered data set was annotated with the point cloud capable labelling tool available at <https://github.com/ch-sa/labelCloud>. The Figure 6 features the tools and one sample point cloud block with bounding boxes for a safety net and barrier.

Figure 6 LabelCloud point cloud labelling tool with a data set sample and added bounding boxes for a safety net (blue) and barrier (green).

3.2. Object Detection Model

See the updated deliverable D2.4 Detailed Description of the Safety Functionalities and Worker Notifications for more general information of the PointPillars object detection model. Here we discuss some practicalities and the results achieved with it.

The intermediate representation of the PointPillars architecture is based on representing a group of points as pillar shaped voxels. These voxels or pillars are discretizing the arbitrary points to a fixed set of pillars on the original X-Y plane. The pillars capture and combine an enclosed number points and their related features as vectors which are further reduced in dimensions by the initial pillar feature neural network. The pillar feature network in a sense produces a reduced dimension pseudo image of the pillars or voxels representing the whole point cloud. This pseudo image is then processed by the 2D convolutional networks and detection heads as is the case with many 2D image based detection solutions.

The PointPillars is intended to detect objects of interest in more or less real time feeds from the LIDAR streams. Typically raw LIDAR point clouds are sparse and without stitching pre-processing to a denser representations. The data set available for our purposes, however, was a result of

photogrammetry combining stitched point clouds and photographs of the locations. The pre-processing steps required for creating a training dataset are described earlier in this section.

The selected implementation of PointPillars in Open3D-ML library supports the use of KITTI formatted point clouds in training data. In order to use this implementation of the PointPillars model, Open3D and Open3D-ML libraries are required. For installation of those follow the respective documentation. To use Open3D-ML's PointPillars implementation a separate data feeder was created to accommodate our requirements and the custom training data set. This data feeder is available at https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_3D_safety_detection/blob/main/ml3d/datasets/bimprovekitti.py. For installation of it follow the instructions and procedures of Open3D-ML library itself and https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_3D_safety_detection#readme. After installation, the Open3D-ML requires creation of the bounding box cache as initial step before any training attempts. See the instructions.

The training of the PointPillars model is started with

```
#python3 scripts/run_pipeline.py torch -c ./V0_pointpillars_bimprovekitti.yml --dataset_path  
<path_to_your_dataset> --pipeline ObjectDetection
```

This uses hyperparameters and other settings included the V0_pointpillars_bimprovekitti.yml file (also available at https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_3D_safety_detection/blob/main/V0_pointpillars_bimprovekitti.yml). This command uses PyTorch as machine learning framework, also Tensorflow versions are supported. Trials in this setup showed that AdamW with weight decay mechanism leads to better results. The availability of stable implementation of AdamW, at the moment, is limited to PyTorch platform only. Open3D-ML informs about stability problems of the AdamW on the Tensorflow.

The resulting model was not properly tested in practice yet. The Open3D-ML reports the following mean average precision, mAP@70, results for the commonly available KITTI data sets in detecting car, pedestrian and cyclist.

Model / Dataset	KITTI [BEV / 3D] @ 0.70
PointPillars (tf)	61.6 / 55.2
PointPillars (torch)	61.2 / 52.8
PointRCNN (tf)	78.2 / 65.9
PointRCNN (torch)	78.2 / 65.9

In our limited data set the model was able reach mAP levels 80-90 for safety nets and 15-20 for barriers on BEV or Birds-Eye-View. The results were @ unrestricted IoU level unlike the public Open3D-ML ones that are on @0.70. From the experience of labelling the point clouds and now in the light of the result, it is obvious that the barriers were less common items on the data set. For a brief definition of terms mAP and IoU, see the deliverable D3.3 Proof of Concept System Description and Test Results.

The integration to ROVAS may be realized e.g. by creating a separate service interface for it. On the other hand, the more automated training data labelling process may be achieved with the 2D image detection model. This requires the availability of the synchronized images and the point clouds intended for the photogrammetry process. The image object detection would detect the objects on the images which would translate to a partial 2D detectable objects' region proposals on the correct spots on the point clouds.

4. Risk and Image Data Management Service

The purpose of the BIMprove Risk and Image Data Management Service is to store and provide access to the data created by the Safety Related Visual Object Detection described above. The Risk and Image Data Management Service includes three main parts that are:

1. The database used to store the metadata provided by the Safety Related Visual Object Detection. The selected database solution is Apache Fuseki graph database that supports RDF (Resource Description Framework) format and SPARQL query language. The database structure follows the risk data ontology specifically developed to address the requirements of risk data management. A visualization of the ontology is shown in Figure 7.
2. REST interface that provides an access to the database. The interface includes two basic access methods that are insert data and query data. The interface is implemented using Python language and Tornado web framework with its asynchronous networking library.
3. HTML based GUI that enables examining the content of the database (as well as the results of the Safety Related Visual Object Detection). The GUI is supported by the Flask micro web framework written in Python.

Figure 7 Risk ontology

The source code implementing the aforementioned modules is available at https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_rdc. In the following sections the installation and usage of the Risk and Image Data Management Service is explained.

4.1. Installation of the Risk and Image Data Management Service

As a prerequisite you should install Python3 into your deployment machine.

Fuseki database and the interface implementing the provided functionalities can be installed with the following instructions:

1. Install and start Fuseki

a) Download Fuseki database deployment files from <https://jena.apache.org/documentation/fuseki2/>

b) Navigate to the folder you saved the files and start Fuseki with the following command:

```
'command ./fuseki-server --mem /ds'
```

c) Navigate to <http://localhost:3030/> (or whatever URL your Fuseki instance is deployed on) and create a new Dataset called "constructionSiteRiskData"

2. Install and start Risk and Image Data Management Service

a) Download the Github repository https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_rdc, unzip the files and navigate to folder ImageMetadataStorage/DatabaseInterface

b) Execute command:

```
python3 fusekiProxy.py
```

c) Open folder ImageMetadataStorage/html and execute command:

```
python3 app.py
```

d) Open your web browser and navigate to URL <http://localhost:8081/> (in case you are running the code in your local machine). If you see an empty table with the title "Safety factor and risk detection results" you have installed the service successfully.

4.2. Testing the installation and provided functionalities

To verify the interfaces of the service, you can add test data to the database. The interfaces can be accessed using e.g. CURL tool. The following scripts can be used (please note that the examples are valid for localhost installation):

1. Add data

The add data functionality enables simulating how results generated by the Safety Related Visual Object Detection service are inserted into the database.

```
curl -iX POST \  
  
'http://localhost:8084/fusekiAddImage' \  
  
-H 'Content-Type: text/plain' \  
  
-d '{"imageID": "2MppzXLWeT", "name": "Safetynet", "confidence": "0.44544", "xmax":  
"675.44312", "xmin": "345.86625", "ymax": "876.31249", "ymin": "436.5287", "imageURL":  
"https://bit.ly/3glwtiH", "anchorBoxImageURL": "https://bit.ly/3glwtiH_2"}'
```

As can be seen, many of the elements of the input JSON are similar to the data elements of the ROVAS response. In addition, the input data contains a unique id of the image and two URLs. The first URL leads to a web location where the analysed image is stored. The second image URL points to another version of the same image where the bounding boxes of labelled items (safety net, barrier or trash) are shown. You can verify the data insert operation by navigating to <http://localhost:8081/>, the table should now contain one data instance.

2. Free query

The free query enables executing SPARQL queries against the database.

```
curl -iX POST \  
  
'http://localhost:8084/fusekiQueryData' \  
  
-H 'Content-Type: text/plain' \  
  
-d 'SELECT ?imageId WHERE { ?image <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>  
<http://www.semanticweb.org/safetyOntology#Image>. ?image  
<http://www.semanticweb.org/safetyOntology#hasRiskRelatedObject> "Safetynet".?image  
<http://www.semanticweb.org/safetyOntology#hasImageId> ?imageId}'
```

The shown SPARQL query statement retrieves the IDs of all database objects that a) are instances of the class 'Image' and b) have "Safetynet" as detected safety related object.

5. Integration with the Bimsync platform

As described in D2.4, the developed ROVAS approach was extended by integrating it with the Bimsync platform. This enables seamlessly sharing the results of the safety risk factor detection with the Bimsync. In more detail, once the user has initiated the safety risk factor detection process with selected photographs, the results produced by ROVAS are automatically transferred to the Bimsync platform using its REST API v2.

To establish this feature, a dedicated Python application called “Bimsync proxy” was developed. The application acts as proxy between the safety risk factor detection application (i.e. ROVAS) and the Bimsync platform and transforms the detection result data into a format and structure understood by Bimsync. Finally, by utilizing the API provided by the Bimsync, it creates new BFC issues that contain the obtained image analysis results and corresponding metadata. In this section, the installation and usage of the Bimsync proxy application is explained in more detail.

5.1. Installation of the Bimsync proxy

The installation of the Bimsync proxy is relatively straightforward. The only prerequisite you should install into your deployment machine is Python3.

- a) Download the Github repository https://github.com/superdupercodez/bimprove_rdc, unzip the files (if needed) and navigate to folder ‘Bimsync_proxy’
- b) Execute command:

```
python3 BCF_proxy.py
```

5.2. Testing the installation and provided functionalities

To verify the behavior of the installed service, you can add test data to Bimsync, which means creating new BFC issues that are based on simulated safety risk factor detection cases. The functionality of the ROVAS approach can imitated using e.g., CURL or Postman tools. The following CURL script can be used to test the behavior of the Bimsync proxy application and its communication with the Bimsync.

```
curl -iX POST \  
  
'http://localhost:8084/ImageToBCF' \  
  
-H 'Content-Type: text/plain' \  
  
-d '{"imageID": "1649830721_t_DJI_0090.JPG_9207b0b3-baf1-11ec-97e1-008cfa000868",  
"name": "barrier", "confidence": "0.2891139686", "xmax": "5458.4936523438", "xmin":  
"4344.3857421875", "ymax": "1997.2319335938", "ymin": "1632.37109375",
```

```
"localOrigFileName": "1649830721_t_DJI_0090.JPG", "localAnchorFileName":  
"1649830721_bbxes_t_DJI_0090.JPG", "imageURL": "https://fasolt4.willab.fi:8883/public/8f80bc87d89b",  
"anchorBoxImageURL": "https://fasolt4.willab.fi:8883/public/433944456c8a"}
```

If the script is executed successfully, you should see a new BFC issue containing the above shown data appearing in Bimsync. Please note that you should edit the relevant parameters (e.g., imageURL and anchorBoxImageURL) to correspond the locations of the images in your deployment environment.

6. Asset Localization and Tracking

Testing of a distributed Asset Localization and Tracking (ALT) system developed in WP3 was performed at Fystikkbakken 14 in the period 2022-09-24/P4D. The system is based on tracking of BLE beacons and uses BluEpyc EchoBeacons, BluEpyc Gateways, GlobalTag tag beacons, and a PC running Debian GNU/Linux as a base station. The software is released under LGPLv3.0 and can be found at <https://bitbucket.org/sintef-manufacturing/ble-tracking/src/master/>. Raw experiment data out of the Gateways was sampled and stored for later tuning and experimenting with and tuning of parameters. The experiment data was stored at <https://bitbucket.org/sintef-manufacturing/ble-tracking-fyrstikkbakken-2022-09/src/master/>. A short description of the experiments at Fyrstikkbakken 14 and some initial observations from experimenting with the recorded data is found as an entry in D3.1 Technology Demonstrations (version 3, M25).

7. References

[1] Redmon, J., Divvala, S., Girshick, R., and Farhadi, A., “You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection”, <http://arxiv.org/abs/1506.02640>, 2015.